

MOBIDATALAB

Labs for prototyping future mobility data sharing solutions in the cloud

| D6.2 - Reporting on MobiDataLab Events #1

23/01/2023

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Summary sheet

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Abstract	This document lists all the events (in addition to the Living Labs instances) and documents the feedback from the activities and participants

Legal Disclaimer

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Project partners

Organisation	Country	Abbreviation
AKKA I&S	France	AKKA
CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO PER L'OTTIMIZZAZIONE E LA RICERCA OPERATIVA	Italy	ICOOR
AETHON SYMVOULI MICHANIKI MONOPROSOPI IKE	Greece	AETHON
CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	Italy	CNR
HOVE	France	HOVE
HERE GLOBAL B.V.	Netherlands	HERE
KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN	Belgium	KUL
UNIVERSITAT ROVIRA I VIRGILI	Spain	URV
POLIS - PROMOTION OF OPERATIONAL LINKS WITH INTEGRATED SERVICES	Belgium	POLIS
F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED	Ireland	F6S

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Executive Summary

This document corresponds to Deliverable 6.2 Reporting on MobiDataLab Events #1 of Task 6.3 Promoting MobiDataLab through events, as part of WP6 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation.

It lists all the events organised and/or co-organised by MobiDataLab and/or in which partners have participated either with a speaker or booth slot to communicate key findings between February 2021 and January 2022. It documents the feedback from the activities and participants and showcases how the project is being promoted to external stakeholders through internal and external events.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PTA	Public Transport Authority
PTO	Public Transport Operator
WP	Work Package

Introduction

1.1. Project Overview

1.

There has been an explosion of mobility services and data sharing in recent years. Building on this, the EU-funded MobiDataLab project works to foster the sharing of data amongst transport authorities, operators, and other mobility stakeholders in Europe. MobiDataLab develops knowledge as well as a cloud solution aimed at easing the sharing of data. Specifically, the project is based on a continuous co-development of knowledge and technical solutions. It collects and analyses the advice and recommendations of experts and supporting cities, regions, clusters, and associations. These actions are assisted by the incremental construction of a cross-thematic knowledge base and a cloud-based service platform, which will improve access and usage of data sharing resources.

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

This Deliverable intends to list all the events organised and/or co-organised by MobiDataLab and/or in which partners have participated either with a speaker or a booth slot to communicate key findings between February 2021 (M1) and January 2022 (M12). It documents the feedback from the activities and participants and showcases how the project is being promoted to external stakeholders through internal and external events.

This document follows the strategy for events included in Deliverable 6.1 Dissemination Report (May 2021), that guides the dissemination activities within MobiDataLab.

1.3. Intended Audience & Review process

The dissemination level of this Deliverable is “public” (PU), and it is mainly addressed to the public, for a better understanding of MobiDataLab’s outreach activities. While all partners are responsible for participating in external events as a speaker or by having a booth and taking advantage of already established events either external or organised by partners’ networks, F6S in collaboration with POLIS, as WP6 Coordinator, and other partners (AKKA, HOVE and HERE) will be the main responsible for the organisation and/or co-organisation of MobiDataLab’s internal events.

It is important to note that this is the first of three Deliverables that will be submitted with the same purpose, to report on MobiDataLab’s events. Deliverable 6.3 Report on MobiDataLab events #2 will list all events from February 2022 and January 2023 and Deliverable 6.4 Report on MobiDataLab events #3 will list all events from February 2023 and January 2024, including the project’s final event.

1.4. Structure of the deliverable and its relationship with other work packages/deliverables

This document first presents the rationale behind MobiDataLab's strategy for organising and participating in events to showcase the project's results as included in the Deliverable 6.1 Dissemination Plan (May 2021, M4). It then describes in detail each internal event organised and/or co-organised by MobiDataLab and external events in which partners have participated either with a speaker or booth slot, between February 2021 and January 2022. Finally, it exposes the impact of such events for the project so far and showcases the planned events for 2022, as the project enters its 2nd year.

2021 MobiDataLab Events

2.1. Rationale as included in the Dissemination Plan

2.

The MobiDataLab project plans to organise its own online and face-to-face dissemination events, as well as take advantage of other established events, including those events organised by partner networks, beyond the events organised in the scope of the virtual and living labs of WP5. Dissemination opportunities will also be sought in other relevant events, including those targeted at transport practitioners, researchers, policymakers and the start-up community, among others.

All partners are expected to contribute to the dissemination of MobiDataLab's results by publishing papers on selected conferences, attending workshops and events, and presenting the results in booths and relevant fora. This will be monitored by F6S through an "Events log", shared with partners and regularly monitored in WP6 internal meetings.

According to the events' rationale as included in Deliverable 6.1 Dissemination Plan (May 2021, M4), the project considers two types of events to promote its outreach activities, as follows:

- (i) Internal events – organisation of online and face-to-face dissemination events to provide tangible experiences on the project's results, with the organisation of, at least, one Webinar per year (three in total) to communicate key findings of the project to relevant stakeholders, and the organisation of a final event by F6S (country still to be defined), with the support of all partners, to be held towards the end of the project to present MobiDataLab's main findings to relevant stakeholders.
- (ii) External events – presentation in, at least, three international scientific conferences, summits, workshops, and other relevant community events per year (nine in total), organised by or associated with partners or by other external entities (scouting or by invitation), including the Annual Polis Conference, which attracts +500 delegates from across the transport spectrum.

Short videos and blog posts published on the project's website may be developed, presenting key moments, short testimonials or the recap of the events organised by the partners or by the partners' network. Moreover, all events are to be listed on the project's website either as "[upcoming](#)" (if still to be held) or "[archived](#)" (once completed).

2.2. Internal Events

2.2.1. *MobiDataLab Webinar #1*

Organisation of the MobiDataLab 1st Webinar

✓ **Topic: “Fostering a data sharing culture for a better mobility in Europe”**

As this was the project’s first Webinar, the objectives, tools, challenges, and main achievements of the project to further promote a mobility data sharing culture in Europe were presented. Moreover, key insights were provided on (i) who the relevant actors for mobility data sharing are, how lack of data impacts them and what their needs are (with the presentation of some proposals on how they can collaborate to address those challenges) and (ii) what the status of the mobility data sharing market is – which are the companies, products and services already operating in Europe.

Since the Webinar was not supposed to be technical (which is the aim of the workshops organised for the MobiDataLab reference group under Task 6.4 Multi-stakeholders group creation and coordination), it targeted the public, which includes all stakeholders interested in mobility and data sharing topics. To reach out to more participants, it focused on the wider topic of data sharing and highlighted MobiDataLab’s main findings regarding the actors’ needs and market analysis. Moreover, other EU projects (DataPorts, Moliere and SoBigData++) were also invited to join a panel discussion, briefly presenting their project, and focusing on what they were doing to foster a data sharing culture in Europe, either in the transport and mobility sector or others.

Before the Webinar, the Webinar concept and a dissemination strategy were drafted by F6S and shared with the partners. The official visual, email-invitation, registration link and social media posts were sent to all partners to share among their organisation and with their external networks. A social media strategy was also discussed with POLIS.

The Webinar was published on the project’s website and a registration page was created. After the Webinar, a blog post was published with the key highlights of the Webinar, the video recording was published on MobiDataLab’s YouTube channel and the project’s website and the Webinar was moved to “archived” on the project website.

✓ **Date: November 25th, 2021**

✓ **Location: Online**

Figure 1 - MobiDataLab 1st Webinar presentation

- ✓ **Agenda / Schedule:** 09.00am – 11.00am

2. Agenda

09:35	The MobiDataLab project in a nutshell <i>Thierry Chevalier, Project Coordinator, AKKA</i>
09:55	Who are the relevant actors for mobility data sharing, what are their needs and how can they cooperate? <i>Stella Noutsou, AETHON</i>
10:05	What is the status of the mobility data sharing market? <i>Didier De Ryck, from KISIO</i>
10:15	Q&A
10:20	Panel discussion – the importance of a data sharing culture in Europe: main challenges and opportunities <i>Moderator: Suzanne Hoadley, from POLIS</i> <i>Panelists: Josep Laborda, Project Coordinator Moliere, FACTUAL Consulting, Roberto Trasarti, Project Coordinator SoBigData++, CNR ISTI</i>
10:50	Q&A
10:55	Closing remarks

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Figure 2 - MobiDataLab 1st Webinar Agenda

- ✓ **Facilitator:** Inês MELO E FARO, F6S
- ✓ **Presentation:**
 - Thierry CHEVALLIER, AKKA Technologies
 - Stella NOUTSOU, AETHON
- ✓ **Attendees:** 37 participants

✓ **Web link:**

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BI9JBkFWteA> (video recording)

2.3. External Events

2.3.1. 4th SOBIGDATA++ Awareness Panel

✓ **Topic: Mobility data sharing: application potential and ethical issues.**

✓ **Date: June 10th, 2021**

✓ **Location: online**

✓ **Agenda / Schedule:**

- 3.00pm - 4.15pm: About decentralized anonymisation of mobility data, data sovereignty in the connected vehicle, studying population dynamics without compromising people's privacy, mobility data reidentification opportunities and risks, and the MobiDataLab project.
 - 3.30pm – 3.45pm: About MobiDataLab Project, a presentation was made by Thierry CHEVALLIER (AKKA)

Figure 3 - Presentation of MobiDataLab Project by Thierry-Xavier CHEVALLIER

✓ **Speakers:**

- Josep DOMINGO-FERRER (Universitat Rovira i Virgili, CATALONIA)
- Frederick RICHTER (Foundation for Data Protection, GERMANY)
- Thierry CHEVALLIER (AKKA Technologies, FRANCE)
- René PERALTA (NIST, USA)
- Giovanni COMANDE (Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, ITALY)

- ✓ **Attendees:** around 35 experts in IT and data privacy
- ✓ **Web links:**
 - https://crises-deim.urv.cat/SBD_awareness_panel/
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cZ3ZjMY4hmU> (video recording)

2.3.2. OGC Mobility Data Science Summit Preview Sessions

- ✓ **Topic: OGC Mobility Summit Preview**
- ✓ **Date: September 15th, 2021**
- ✓ **Location:** online
- ✓ **Agenda / Schedule:**
 - 2.00pm – 3.30pm
- ✓ **Facilitator:** Scott SIMMONS, Chief Standards Officer, OGC
- ✓ **Presentation:** Johannes LAUER, Principal Technical Product Manager, HERE Technologies
- ✓ **Speakers:**
 - Scott SIMMONS, Chief Standards Officer, OGC
 - George PERCIVALL, Engineer, Geo-Roundtable
 - Mahmoud SAKR, Professor, Université Libre de BRUXELLES (ULB)
 - Kim KYOUNG-SOOK, Researcher, National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science & Technology (AIST)
 - Anita GRASER, Scientist, AIT AUSTRIAN Institute of Technology (Vienna, AUSTRIA)
 - Johannes LAUER, Principal Technical Product Manager, HERE Technologies
 - Dr Pin KUNG, Assistant Researcher, SkyEyes GPS Technology Co., Lt
 - Martin DESCRUISSEAUX, Engineer, GeoMatys.com
- ✓ **Web links:**
 - <http://www.geoworks.sg/programmes/singapore-geospatial-festival/sqgeofest-2021-schedule/sqgeofest-2021-schedule/15-september-2021>
 - [OGC Mobility Summit Preview \(video recording\)](#)

2.3.3. OGC Mobility Data Science Summit

✓ **Topic: OGC Mobility Summit**

Almost every activity in our modern life leaves a digital trace, typically including location and time. Either captured by a sensor, manually input calendar item, or extracted from a social media post, the increase in the volume, variety, and velocity of spatiotemporal data nowadays is unprecedented. The ability to manage and analyse this data is important for many application domains, including smart cities, health, transportation, agriculture, sports, biodiversity, etc. Since the civilian use of GPS was allowed in 1980, followed by the technological advances in other location tracking systems – Wi-Fi, RFID, Bluetooth, etc, it is becoming more and more easy to track moving objects.

The Mobility Data Science Summit discussed the challenges of managing this data and making sense of it, with a focus on the tooling and standardization requirements.

Data science is commonly known as the pipeline of methods and tools from data acquisitions, until the delivery of useful insights, going through data cleaning, integration, management, and analysis. Many tools exist for helping data scientists in every step in this pipeline.

Yet mobility data has its own characteristics that cannot be handled by the common data science tools. Mobility data is typically available in the form of sequences of location points with time stamps, that are generated by location tracking devices. So, it is both multidimensional and time series data, a structure that requires special data science tools and methods.

OGC has proactively envisioned the need for specialized data model and exchange formats and formed work groups including moving features SWG and Temporal DWG. It is also natural that the temporal concepts found their way to the work of other work groups, such as GeoPose. This summit is a chance to synchronize across work groups, and to align the concepts.

✓ **Date: December 08th, 2021**

✓ **Location:** Hybrid – online and Singapore

✓ **Agenda / Schedule:**

- Opening 15 mins: Mahmoud SAKR
- Presentation session 2h
- Panel 1h of the five speakers interactive with audience, moderate by Mahmoud SAKR
- Closing note: Nobuhiro ISHIMARU
- Summit reporting: Scott SIMMONS

✓ **Summit Goals:**

- Understand the technical challenges of Mobility Data Science
- Harmonize the concepts of “spatiotemporal” and “trajectory” across Working Groups.

✓ **Objectives:**

- Identify new standardization requirements
- Identify and link the mobility-related work in the different Working Groups
- Align the mobility-related terms and concepts

✓ **Speakers:**

- Mahmoud SAKR
- Mohamed MOKBLE, University of MINNESOTA, QARTA Accurate Map Services
- Cheng FU, University of ZURICH, H2020 Project Tack&Know
- Johannes LAUER, HERE Technologies, H2020 Project mobidatalab.eu
- Steve LIANG, University of CALGARY, Mobility and IoT data for complex physical operations – SensorUp case studies
- Kim KYOUNG-SOOK, AIST JAPAN, OGC API for Moving Features
- Nobuhiro ISHIMARU
- Scott SIMMONS, Chief Standards Officer, OGC

2.3.4. *Challenge « Tourism and Mobility », Mêlée Numérique pitch competition*

✓ **Topic: Tourism and Mobility Challenge**

MobiDataLab was chosen as a member of the jury for a regional challenge around Mobility at the main digital event in Occitania, South of France (namely “[la Mêlée numérique](#)”). The principle was quite similar to the hackathons the project aims to organize in the framework of the Living & Virtual Labs (WP5): in this case the regional authority proposed a challenge (i.e. how to bring visitors to regional tourist sites using low-carbon transport modes) and a dozen start-ups applied with innovative solutions.

✓ **Date: December 08th, 2021**

✓ **Location: Toulouse, FRANCE**

✓ **Facilitators:**

- Alix HOWARD, Digital transformation and change management consultant, SQLI
- Bastien INGWEILLER, Head of innovation, La Mêlée

✓ **Jury:**

- Matias ESTANO, CEO « Le Starter »
- Jean MICOUD, Managing Director, Comité Départemental du Tourisme de Haute-Garonne

- Hubert FAURE, Président and Founder « Domaine de Montjoie »
- Manuel MIRABEL, CEO “Ctoutvert”
- Myriam LLUSCA, Data Manager, CDT
- Thierry CHEVALLIER, Coordinator H2020 MobiDataLab, AKKA
- Alain CAUHAUPE, Responsable TER liO Occitanie SNCF
- Alain VINCENT, Haute-Garonne Numérique
- Marc TRUBERT, Director of Development of Occitanie Tourism Fund, M Capital

✓ **Awards:**

The following start-ups were awarded:

- FULLBUS in the category “Tourism & Mobility solution” – Fullbus aims to complement the empty trips of bus companies by offering travellers a new way to travel, more economical and more responsible.
- IODINES: in the category “Tourism & Mobility initiative” – Iodines is a Toulouse-based carsharing start-up who proposed to extend their services to non-urban areas.
- UWINKIKE: in the category “Jury’s favourite” – Uwinbike is an innovative solution to encourage and reward the use of active mobility

Figure 4 - Awarded Start-ups

- ✓ **Attendees:** 7300 overall @ La Melee numérique 2021
- ✓ **Web links:**
 - https://youtu.be/clc_BU-Luvk?t=29542 (video recording)

2.3.5. RNTP 2021

✓ **Topic: RNTP 2021**

RNTP stands for “Rencontres Nationales du Transport Public” (National Meetings on Public Transport). This is the most important event related to public transport sector in France.

Bertrand BILLOUD (VP Communication, HOVE) had a 35 minutes talk about the importance of commons, in the digital sector, as a success key factor for cooperation and digital sovereignty, governance between public and private stakeholders. MobiDataLab project was mentioned during this task.

✓ **Date: September 29th, 2021**

✓ **Location :** Toulouse Exhibition & Convention Centre – MEET, France

✓ **Agenda / Schedule:**

- 12.30pm – 01.00pm

Figure 5 - Bertrand BILLOUD (HOVE) speaking at the RNTP Conference

✓ **Speakers:**

- Bertrand BILLOUD, VP Communication, HOVE, FRANCE

✓ **Attendees:** 50 participants assisted the presentation, mostly French Public Transport Authorities (PTA), French Ministry of Transportation and start-ups.

✓ **Web links:**

- <https://www.rencontres-transport-public.fr/programme/communs-numeriques-au-coeur-des-enjeux-de-gouvernance-de-cooperation-et-de-souverainete-des-territoires/>

2.3.6. ITS WORLD CONGRESS

✓ **Topic: ITS WORLD CONGRESS**

The ITS Congress is the biggest event focused on smart mobility and the digitalisation of transport. Every year, ERTICO organises an ITS regional or World Congress in Europe – in 2021 the ITS World Congress took place on Oct 11-15 in Hamburg, Germany. These Congresses are the yearly celebration of smart mobility: they underline the importance of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), particularly in cities and regions where they are hosted, and are important channels to raise awareness of smart mobility solutions among policy makers, experts and the general public. They include live sessions where industry experts present the latest developments in ITS, a showcase of cutting-edge technology and an exhibition space.

Figure 6 - Polis Booth at the ITS World Congress

The project MobiDataLab was represented in the POLIS Network booth in the exhibition area. A roll-up was displayed at the booth, as well as flyers that were distributed amongst interested participants. Additionally, a live project presentation was carried out at the booth to a small audience by project coordinators AKKA.

- ✓ **Date:** October 11-15th, 2021
- ✓ **Location:** Hamburg, GERMANY
- ✓ **Organizer:** ERTICO
- ✓ **Facilitator / Booth Hosts:** Laura BABIO SOMOZA & Suzanne HOADLEY, POLIS Network
- ✓ **Speakers:**
 - Benoit BAURENS, H2020 MobiDataLab Director, AKKA Technologies

Figure 7 - Benoit BAURENS presenting the MobiDataLab project at the ITS World Congress

- ✓ **Attendees:**
 - Estimated to the event: 10,000
 - Estimated to POLIS Booth: 200
 - Participants profiles: PTA and PTO (Public Transport Operators)
- ✓ **Web link:**
 - <https://www.imcmobilitycongress.com/en/>

2.3.7. POLIS ANNUAL CONFERENCE

✓ **Topic: POLIS Annual Conference**

The POLIS Annual Conference provides an opportunity for cities and regions to showcase their transport achievements and innovations to a large audience of mobility experts, practitioners and decision makers.

MobiDataLab flyers were distributed at the POLIS stand in the exhibition area, interacting with those interested stakeholders.

✓ **Date: December 01st-02nd, 2021**

✓ **Location: Götehnburg, SWEDEN**

✓ **Facilitator / Booth Hosts:** Laura BABIO SOMOZA & Suzanne HOADLEY, POLIS Network

✓ **Attendees:**

- Estimated to the event: 600
- Interested in MobiDataLab at POLIS Stand: 50
- Participants profiles: PTA and PTO (Public Transport Operators)

✓ **Web link:**

- <https://www.polisnetwork.eu/2021-annual-polis-conference/>

Monitoring Impact

3.1. KPIs monitoring and impact

3.

As described in Deliverable 6.1 Dissemination Plan, 3 KPIs have been established in relation to the organisation and participation in events. These KPIs were not established at the proposal stage and, thus, are a direct result of the agreement between partners regarding their inclusion in Deliverable 6.1. and are regularly monitored by F6S under Task 6.3. Promoting MobiDataLab through events, to enhance their performance, outreach, and overall impact.

The KPIs related to the organisation and participation in events are as follows:

KPI	Expected performance					
	Year 1		Year 2		Year 3	
	Target:	Achieved	Target:	Achieved	Target:	Achieved
Number of final event attendees	-	-	-	-	100-150	
Number of representations at events	≥3	7	≥3		≥3	
Number of participants in awareness events	≥20	37	20-50		20-50	

Table 1 - KPIs for organisation and participation in events

Regarding year 1, partners have been present at more than 3 external events between February 2021 and January 2022 (see section 2.3), either with a speaker or a booth slot and MobiDataLab's 1st Webinar, held on the 25th of November 2021 (see section 2.2.1), was gathered 37 participants. Both KPIs for year 1 were, thus, achieved.

Regarding the impact of these activities, as this was the project's first year, it was still too early to show major results and progress on the project activities. Nevertheless, all participations at external events were able to showcase the initial outcomes of the project, positioning MobiDataLab as a project to follow among the community, and the 1st MobiDataLab Webinar brought together several relevant actors of the project, increasing the outreach of its activities.

Below is a list of the events organised by MobiDataLab or in which partners participated between February 2021 and January 2022.

Event's name	MobiDataLab's contribution	Date and location	Audience	Estimated n° of attendees
4th SOBIGDATA++ Awareness Panel	Keynote speaker on mobility data sharing	10/06/2021 Online	Research and academic community	20-30
OGC Mobility Data Science Summit Preview Session	Panel discussion on mobility data science	15/09/2021 Hybrid (Singapore and online)	Industry, startups, researchers, policymakers	10
Challenge "Tourism and Mobility", Mêlée Numérique pitch competition	Jury member at mobility hackathon	29/09/2021 Hybrid (Haute-Garonne, France and online)	Industry and startups, transport and regional authorities	7,300
RNTP 2021	Presentation on digital commons	29/09/2021 Toulouse, France	Industry, startups, researchers, policymakers	50
ITS World Congress	Booth with information on MobiDataLab	15/10/2021 Hamburg, Germany	Industry, startups, researchers, policymakers, transport authorities	200
MobiDataLab Webinar #1	1 st project Webinar to showcase initial results	25/11/2021 Online	General public	37
Polis Annual Conference	Booth with information on MobiDataLab	01/12/2021 Gothenburg, Sweden	Industry, startups, researchers, policymakers, transport authorities	50

Table 2 - List of events organised by MobiDataLab or in which MobiDataLab participated

Whilst the COVID pandemic has not constituted a major issue for the project to achieve its KPIs and participate actively in events, it is worth noting that the scale of events and participation levels might be affected overall and is likely to continue to affect events' participation and involvement in 2022 as the pandemic perdures. This will also be factored into the project's events activities and impact analysis.

3.2. Foreseen events for 2022

Below is a non-exclusive list of events foreseen for 2022, either organised by MobiDataLab or in which partners expect to take part.

It is important to note that these are the events already identified as relevant for MobiDataLab's participation, meaning that several others might be considered over the course of the project's 2nd year, particularly with the submission of scientific publications at international conferences to showcase the project's results.

Event's name	Date and location	MobiDataLab's contribution
IT-TRANS International Conference and Exhibition 2022 (Intelligent Urban Transport Systems)	08-10/03/2022 Karlsruhe Trade Fair Centre, Germany	Call for speakers Participant, networking
Techchill	27-29/04/2022 Hybrid (Riga, Latvia and online)	Call for speakers Participant, networking
ITS Toulouse	30/05-02/06/2022 Toulouse, France	Call for speakers Participant, networking
The Next Web Annual Conference	16-17/06/2022 Amsterdam, The Netherlands	Call for speakers Participant, networking
State of the Map 2022 OpenStreetMap annual conference	To be Defined	Call for speakers Participant, networking
MobiDataLab Webinar #2	November 2022 Online	Main organiser
Transport Research Arena Lisbon 2022	14-17/11/2022 Lisbon, Portugal	Call for papers Participant, networking

Table 3 - MobiDataLab foreseen events for 2022

Conclusions

This Deliverable has identified and listed all the events organised and/or co-organised by MobiDataLab and/or in which partners have participated either with a speaker or a booth slot. The main goal of this outreach activity is to showcase the project results and engage with MobiDataLab's target audiences, which play an important role in the project's dissemination strategy.

Overall, as this was the project's first year, the events in which partners participated between February 2021 and January 2022 had a moderate impact on MobiDataLab, since the project was still in the process of achieving its first results. However, it is important to note that all these events contributed to an increased awareness of the project, its activities, and goals as they targeted specific audiences and, thus, not only the KPIs but also the foreseen impact are believed to have been achieved.

Moreover, the MobiDataLab 1st Webinar was attended by 37 participants from relevant stakeholders in a lively discussion on how to promote a data sharing culture in Europe in the mobility sector, which also contributed to the creation of a community willing to follow the project's future activities.

MobiDataLab consortium

The consortium of MobiDataLab consists of 10 partners with multidisciplinary and complementary competencies. This includes leading universities, networks and industry sector specialists.

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